

Do you know what "irreducible" means? To explain what it is, let's dive into an abstract topic.

Eisenstein's Criterion

The main point of testing if a polynomial satisfies all the divisibility criteria, is to prove that it is irreducible over the rationals(Q). A more mathematical way of putting it is:

“A polynomial is irreducible over a field F if it cannot be written as a product of lower-degree polynomials with coefficients in F”

Reducible means that a polynomial can have two or more factors with rational coefficients. For example, six can be broken down into three and two. The word used in the phrase above is irreducible, meaning that a polynomial cannot be broken down into smaller factors with rational coefficients. An integer example of this would be seven. The factors are seven and one, meaning seven is prime.

Six and seven are integers not polynomials, so why does it matter?

For a “prime” polynomial, e.g. $x^2 + 3$, the polynomial is irreducible (the root is complex). Just like the prime example number seven: this prime, irreducible polynomial can only be factored into one and itself.

A reducible polynomial could be $x^2 + 4x + 4$, this has two \mathbb{Q} roots, -2 and -2. Another way to connect this reducible polynomial to a composite integer like 6 (as given in the example above) is to see that it has many factors, aside from itself. A larger composite polynomial would look something along the line of $2x^2 + 4x + 4$, it has three factors, $2(x+2)(x+2)$.

Now let's dive into the criteria that a polynomial has to meet to be irreducible over Q.

If a polynomial exists such that $f(x) = a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0$

With integer coefficients and a p that...

$$p \nmid a_n$$

$$p^2 \nmid a_0$$

$$p \mid a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}$$

Then $f(x)$ is irreducible over Q.

Working example:

- $x^4 + 2x^3 + 4x^2 + 8x + 6$
- Our p is going to be 2
- $2 \mid 2, 4, 8, \text{ and } 6$
- Our leading coefficient is 1
- $p \nmid 1$

- Yet, $2^2 = 4 \nmid 6$
- Since $p^2 \nmid 6$, the polynomial is irreducible over \mathbb{Q}
- So for this polynomial Eisenstein's criterion is applicable to this polynomial

Why does p matter?

Eisenstein's criterion requires $p \nmid$ by the leading term but it must be divisible by all the other coefficients. p^2 must not divide into the constant term, and if all three of these criteria hold, then the polynomial is irreducible over the rationals.

Failed example:

For the polynomial $x^4 + 12x^3 + 10x^2 + 24x + 8$ such that,
 $p = 2$, the leading coefficient $a_4 = 1$

$$2 \nmid 1$$

$$2 \mid 12, 10, 24 \text{ and } 8$$

$$4 \mid 8.$$

The polynomial almost satisfied the criterion, yet the criterion failed on the constant term such that $p^2 \mid 8$, the square of our p divided into our constant term. Meaning for this polynomial we cannot use Eisenstein's Criterion.

How come we divide by p^2 and not just p ? - Lets solve a polynomial to prove:

$$x^2 + 6x + 9$$

Let p be 3

$$3 \nmid 1$$

$$3 \mid 6$$

$3^2 \mid 9$, the polynomial could be reducible

$$x^2 + 6x + 9 = (x + 3)(x + 3)$$

Though don't be confused, this doesn't apply to every single polynomial, Eisenstein's Criterion "misses" quite a few polynomials. A more mathematical way of putting this would be the following: the criterion is sufficient but not necessary for a polynomial to be irreducible.

An example of this would be a polynomial like so:

$$x^2 - 2x - 3.$$

Let p be 3, p divides into the constant term only, meaning that Eisenstein's Criterion failed for this example.

The polynomial is still reducible: $x^2 - 2x - 3 = (x - 3)(x + 1)$, however the polynomial didn't pass the criterion, proving that the criterion is sufficient to prove that a polynomial is irreducible, but not necessary.

This criterion proves if a polynomial satisfies all of the conditions then it is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} . If Eisenstein's criterion fails then the polynomial could still have factors.

Ever heard of the phrase quality over quantity? That's what this criterion is, it doesn't solve the vast swathes of every single polynomial, but rather it solves certain ones precisely, fast and perfectly.

Sites used:

Polynomials, Integer, and Yufei Zhao. *MOP 2007 Black Group*. 2007.

“What's a Prime Polynomial? | Printable Summary | Virtual Nerd.” *Virtualnerd.com*, 2026, www.virtualnerd.com/worksheetHelper.php?tutID=Alg1_7_2_6. Accessed 30 Mar. 2026.

“Eisensteins Irreducibility Criterion - Wolfram|Alpha.” *Wolframalpha.com*, 2016, www.wolframalpha.com/input/?i=eisensteins+irreducibility+criterion. Accessed 24 Mar. 2026.